

INTERNATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS TREATIES AND THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: SUCCESSES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract. In recent years the law of treaties in Uzbekistan has evolved in different fields, including treaty-making practice in international human rights law. After the proclamation of independence the Republic of Uzbekistan paid a huge attention to the ratification/accession to core human rights treaties. However, only joining international conventions could not and cannot provide citizens and the government with full respect for and protection of core human rights.

The Article discusses the notion of treaties in international law as a main source and an approach of the legal system of Uzbekistan to international treaties on the basis of the existing theories, illustrated with the comprehensive and reliable examples of the core international human rights treaties.

Key words: international law, human rights, core human rights conventions, treaties ratification, accession, implementation.

Аннотация. Сўнги йилларда Ўзбекистонда шартномавий ҳуқуқ турли соҳаларда, жумладан халқаро инсон ҳуқуқлари соҳасида ҳам амалий жиҳатдан ривожланди. Ўзбекистон Республикаси давлат мустақиллигига эришгандан сўнг, мамлакатда инсон ҳуқуқлари бўйича асосий халқаро шартномаларни ратификация қилиш / уларга қўшилиш масаласига катта эътибор қаратилди. Шунга қарамай, жамиятда инсон ҳуқуқлари тўлиқ ҳурмат қилиниши ва ҳимояланишини таъминлаш учун халқаро конвенцияларга қўшилишнинг ўзигина етарли эмас.

Мақолада халқаро ҳуқуқдаги шартномалар тушунчаси асосий манба сифатида ва Ўзбекистон ҳуқуқ тизимининг халқаро шартномаларга ёндашуви мавжуд назариялар асосида ўрганилган, Ўзбекистоннинг инсон ҳуқуқлари бўйича асосий халқаро шартномаларни ратификация қилиш / уларга қўшилиш борасидаги муваффақиятлари тўлиқ ва ишончли мисоллар асосида ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: халқаро ҳуқуқ, инсон ҳуқуқлари, инсон ҳуқуқлари бўйича асосий конвенциялар, шартномаларни ратификация қилиш, қўшилиш, имплементация.

Аннотация. В последние годы договорное право в Узбекистане развивалось в различных областях, включая договорную практику в международном праве прав человека. После обретения государственной независимости Республика Узбекистан уделяла огромное внимание ратификации/присоединению к основным договорам по правам человека. Однако только присоединение к международным конвенциям не могло и не может обеспечить гражданам и правительству полное соблюдение и защиту основных прав человека.

В статье рассматривается понятие договоров в международном праве как основного источника и подход правовой системы Узбекистана к международным договорам на основе существующих теорий, успехи Узбекистана в ратификации/присоединении к основным международным договорам по правам человека иллюстрируются конкретными примерами.

Ключевые слова: международное право, права человека, основные конвенции по правам человека, ратификация договоров, присоединение, имплементация.

Introduction

Before proceeding to the overall analysis of Uzbekistan's approaches to international human rights treaties, it is more important to explain the sources of international law, particularly, the role of treaties in international law and the legal system and legal framework of Uzbekistan, regulating law of treaties as well as relationship between national law and international law comprehensively.

There are probably few fields of international law where confusion and clarity reign more supreme than that of the sources¹. The sources of international law have been codified in the Statute of the International Court of Justice². Article 38 of the Statute provides that "the Court, whose function is to decide in accordance with international law shall apply..... international conventions, whether general or particular, establishing rules expressly recognized by the contesting States;.....".

The first source referred to in Article 38(1) of the ICJ Statute is "conventions, whether general or particular, establishing rules expressly recognized by the contesting states". As a term of international law, "conventions" are more commonly referred to as "treaties"³.

Much of the recent international law principles related to law-making treaties are codified in the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (hereafter the VCLT). The VCLT sets forth a comprehensive set of rules governing the formation, interpretation, and termination of treaties⁴.

The preamble to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that the republic recognizes the supremacy of universally recognized rules of international law⁵.

The Concept of Foreign Policy of Uzbekistan also determines the strengthening and improvement of the

legal framework of international cooperation, the conclusion of prospective bilateral ratification of multilateral agreements as one of the political and diplomatic tools of a unified state policy.

Therefore, in accordance with the national legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, international agreements as the main sources of international law form the legal framework of interstate relations and are a guarantee for the stability of the obligations of the parties.

The first normative legal act regulating the field of international agreements in Uzbekistan was the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On International Treaties" of December 22, 1995⁶. Within the framework of ensuring the implementation of this law, several decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers have been adopted. With the development of law of treaties wholly, there was a need for renewal of the national legislation as well. Therefore, on February 6, 2019, a new Law "On International Treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (hereinafter "the Law") was adopted⁷. The new Law is an example of an implementation of the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, to which 116 countries are parties as of April 2022⁸.

The Law of Uzbekistan (Article 4) also provides the definition of 'a treaty' like the one given in the VCLT, defining that "...international treaty of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an international agreement concluded in writing by the Republic of Uzbekistan with a foreign state, international organization or other subject having the right to conclude international treaties, which is regulated by international law, regardless of whether it is contained in one document, in two or more related documents among themselves, as well as regardless of its specific name and method of conclusion (contract, agreement, convention, act, pact, protocol, exchange of letters or notes and oth-

¹ G.J.H. van Hoot. (1983). *Rethinking the Sources of International Law*, Deventer/Netherlands: Kluwer Law and Taxation Publishers, at 13, 57-60.

² Statute of the International Court of Justice, 24 October 1945 // Available at: Statute of the Court | International Court of Justice (icj-cij.org).

³ Ademola Abass. (2014). *Complete International Law: Text, Cases, and Materials*, 2nd edn, the United States of America by Oxford University Press, at 77.

⁴ Carter, Weiner, & Hollis. (2018). *International Law*. Wolters Kluwer in New York 7th ed., at 72.

⁵ The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1992. www.lex.uz // <https://www.lex.uz/acts/20596>.

⁶ The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On International Treaties" dated from December 22, 1995, No. 172-I // Available in Uzbek at: 172-I-сон 22.12.1995. O'zbekiston Respublikasining xalqaro shartnomalarit o'g'risida (lex.uz).

⁷ The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On International Treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated from February 6, 2019 // Available in English at: <https://lex.uz/docs/4830084>.

⁸ The Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, 1969 // https://legal.un.org/ilc/texts/instruments/english/conventions/1_1_1969.pdf (The Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to this Convention in accordance with the resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 24, 1995, No. 29-I "On accession to the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties".)

er names and methods of concluding an international agreement)...”⁹.

In international law the terms monism and dualism are used to describe two different theories of the relationship between international law and national law. Monists accept that the internal and international legal systems form a unity. Both national legal rules and international rules which a state has accepted, for example by way of a treaty, determine whether actions are legal or illegal. On the other hand, dualists emphasize the difference between national and international law, and require the translation (incorporation, implementation, or transformation) of the latter into the former. If a state accepts a treaty, then it is required to adapt its national law in order to conform to the treaty, otherwise the treaty will not be binding on that state and will not be a part of its legal system.

From the nature of its legal system, the Republic of Uzbekistan is considered as a dualist-theory state. Article 3 of the Law of 2019 states that “international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan along with generally recognized principles and norms of international law are an integral part of the legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan¹⁰”. It means that when Uzbekistan ratifies or accedes to any international agreement, it is required to enact implementation act in the form of law or presidential decree/resolution of the Parliament so that this international agreement can be binding on the state and can be a part of its legal system.

Discussion

1. Uzbekistan’s successes in ratification of core international human rights treaties

After gaining independence on September 1, 1991, the Republic of Uzbekistan manifested its commitment and willingness to the full compliance with international human rights standards. To this end, from the beginning of the independence, Uzbekistan attempted to ratify or accede to the core international human rights treaties. As an independent country and a new member of the United Nations, Uzbekistan started focusing on international human rights treaties

and their ratification. The honest attempt can be seen when Uzbekistan ratified the Universal Declaration on Human Rights of 1948 although the document carries non-binding character, and any state is not required to ratify or accede to it¹¹.

Since the independence, the country has acceded to several international treaties, thus marking its intention to move towards the assumption of its responsibilities as a sovereign state and member of the international community. So far, Uzbekistan has acceded to the seven (7) core international human rights instruments, three (3) optional protocols and more than forty (40) human rights-related international conventions (e.g., ILO conventions).

The most important international human rights treaties and their optional protocols ratified by Uzbekistan are as follows¹²:

1. CAT – Convention against Torture and Other Cruel Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment;
2. ICCPR – International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights;
3. ICCPR-OP1 – Optional Protocol to the International Convention on Civil and Political Rights;
4. ICCPR-OP2-DP – Second Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights aiming to the abolition of the death penalty;
5. CEDAW – Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women;
6. CERD – International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination;
7. ICESCR – International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights;
8. CRC – Convention on the Rights of the Child;
9. CRC-OP-AC – Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the involvement of children in armed conflict;
10. CRC-OP-SC – Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the sale of children child prostitution and child pornography;
11. CRPD – Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

⁹ The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On International Treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated from February 6, 2019 // Available in English at: <https://lex.uz/docs/4830084>.

¹⁰ Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On International Treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated from February 6, 2019 // Available in English at: <https://lex.uz/docs/4830084>.

¹¹ The Republic of Uzbekistan ratified the Universal Declaration on Human Rights in accordance with the Resolution of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 1991, No. 366-XII.

¹² More information about ratification/accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to international human rights instruments is available at: Treaty bodies Treaties (ohchr.org).

Below we will elaborate more in detail the ratification process of and historical backgrounds to the core international human rights treaties and their optional protocols.

The first international human rights treaty which the Republic of Uzbekistan acceded was the Convention on the Rights of the Child¹³ (CRC) on 29 June 1994. However, with the connection of its accession to the Convention, the Implementation Act was enacted earlier, that is, on December 9, 1992¹⁴. After the deposit of the accession instrument, the Convention entered into force for Uzbekistan in 1994.

Unlike other forty-seven states parties¹⁵ to the Convention which have accompanied their RUDs (reservations, understandings, and declarations).

It can be noted that 1995 was a kind of the year of the respect for human rights treaties in international relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan when the five most important international human rights treaties and one Optional Protocol entered into force for the republic in 1995.

The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CE-

DAW) entered into force for the Republic of Uzbekistan on 19 Jul 1995. On September 28, 1995, at the same time four (4) core international human rights treaties and one Optional Protocol entered into force for the Republic of Uzbekistan. They are: International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)¹⁶, Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR-OP1)¹⁷, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)¹⁸, International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (CERD)¹⁹ and Convention against Torture and Other Cruel Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CAT)²⁰.

The next phase of ratification/accession period came in 2008 after a long silence. On December 23, 2008, the Republic of Uzbekistan committed to accede to three optional protocols of several core human rights treaties. They are the Second Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights aiming to the abolition of the death penalty (ICCPR-OP2-DP)²¹, the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the involvement

¹³ As of April 2022, 196 states are parties to the Convention // More information is available at: https://treaties.un.org/pages/ShowMTDSGDetails.aspx?src=UNTSO&tabid=2&mtdsg_no=IV-11&chapter=4&lang=en#Participants

¹⁴ The Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to this Convention in accordance with the Resolution of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 9, 1992, No. 757-XII "On Accession to the Convention on the Rights of the Child // Available in Russian at: <http://old.lex.uz/docs/2595909>

¹⁵ More information on RUDs of the States Parties to the CRC is available at: UNTC

¹⁶ The Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to this International Covenant in accordance with the Resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 31, 1995 No. 127-I "On Accession to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights dated December 16, 1966" // Available in Uzbek at: 16.12.1966. Fuqaroviyvasiyosiyhuquqlarto'g'risida (lex.uz)

¹⁷ The Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to this Protocol in accordance with the Resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan of August 31, 1995 No. 128-I "On Accession to the Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of December 16, 1966" // Available in Uzbek at:

16.12.1966. Fuqaroviyvasiyosiyhuquqlarto'g'risidagixalqaropaktgadoir (lex.uz)

¹⁸ The Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to this Convention in accordance with the Resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 31, 1995 No. 126-I "On accession to the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights dated December 16, 1966" // Available in Uzbek at: 126-I-сон 31.08.1995. 1966 йил 16 декабрдаги Иқтисодий, ижтимоий ва маданий ҳуқуқлар тўғрисидаги халқаро пактга қўшилиш ҳақида (lex.uz)

¹⁹ The Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to this Convention in accordance with the Resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 31, 1995 No. 129-I "On Accession to the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination of December 21, 1965" // Available in Uzbek at: 129-I-сон 31.08.1995. 1965-йил 21-декабрдаги Ирқий камситишнинг бarchashakllarin itugatishto 'g'risidagixalqarokonvensiyaga qo'shilish haqida (lex.uz)

²⁰ This Convention was ratified by the Resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan of August 31, 1995 No. 130-I "On Accession to the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment of December 10, 1984" // Available in Uzbek at: 130-I-сон 31.08.1995. 1984-йил 10-декабрдаги Қийноқларга солишгавуomaladabo'lish vajazolashning boshqashafq atsiz, g'ayriinsoniy yoqiqadr-qimmatnitahqirlovchiturlariga qarshikonvensiyaga qo'shilish haqida (lex.uz)

²¹ The Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to this Second Optional Protocol in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2008 No. ZRU-185 "On the Accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Second Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, aiming to the abolition of the death penalty (New York, December 15, 1989)" // Available in Russian at: 15.12.1989. К Международному пакту «О гражданских и политических правах, направленный на отмену смертной казни» (lex.uz).

of children in armed conflict (CRC-OP-AC)²², and the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the sale of children, child prostitution and child pornography (CRC-OP-SC)²³.

The last core human rights instrument which the Republic of Uzbekistan ratified was the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD). Uzbekistan participated in the negotiations of the draft Convention and consequently signed the Convention in 2009. However, the ratification process took more than a decade to be accomplished. In 2021 the Republic of Uzbekistan ratified the Convention with the following declaration and reservation:

“The Republic of Uzbekistan recognizes that persons with disabilities have legal capacity on an equal basis with others in all aspects of their lives.

The Republic of Uzbekistan expresses its understanding that the Convention allows appropriate measures to be taken to ensure that persons with disabilities have access to support and replace decision-making mechanisms, including the limitation of the legal capacity of persons with disabilities, in appropriate circumstances and in accordance with the law.

The Republic of Uzbekistan reserves the right to continue to use alternative decision-making mechanisms in relation to persons with disabilities in appropriate circumstances and subject to appropriate and effective safeguards in the event that Article 12 of the Convention can be interpreted as requiring their abolition.”²⁴

2. Challenges in ratification/accession and implementation of conventions

International human rights regime consists of nine (9) core treaties which every state is expected to be a

party to. The role of these 9 conventions in the international human rights system is significant in a sense that for states seeking to respect, protect and promote human rights, membership in these instruments they determine a reputation and a compliance of those states with the rule of law in the international arena.

As mentioned above, the Republic of Uzbekistan committing itself to be bound by international human rights instruments, has ratified seven (7) of these nine (9) international conventions²⁵, which itself shows the full commitment of Uzbekistan to international human rights protection and promotion. According to the Office of High Commissioner for Human Rights, only several states have ratified those 9 core international human rights treaties²⁶.

However, the Republic of Uzbekistan has failed to ratify the other two core international human rights treaties so far. They are the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of their Families²⁷, and the International Convention for the Protection of all Persons from Enforced Disappearance²⁸.

The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights concluding observations on the third periodic report²⁹ of Uzbekistan also recommends that the State party consider ratifying the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families, and the International Convention for the Protection of All Persons from Enforced Disappearance³⁰.

Furthermore, the Republic of Uzbekistan has not ratified the several optional protocols to the conven-

²² The Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to this Optional Protocol in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 12, 2008 No. ZRU-190 “On the Accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the involvement of children in armed conflicts (New York, May 25, 2000)” // Available in Russian at: 25.05.2000. К Конвенции о правах ребенка, касающийся участия детей в вооруженных конфликтах (lex.uz)

²³ The Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to this Optional Protocol in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 11, 2008 No. ZRU-188 “On the Accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the sale of children, child prostitution and child pornography (New York, May 25, 2000)” // Available in Russian at: 25.05.2000. К Конвенции о правах ребенка, касающийся торговли детьми, детской проституции и детской порнографии (lex.uz).

²⁴ The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (New York, December 13, 2006) dated from June 7, 2021, No. ZRU-695// Available in Uzbek at: O’RQ-695-сон 07.06.2021. Nogironlarhuquqlarito’g’ri sidagiKonvensiyani (Nyu-York, 2006-yil 13-dekabr) ratifikatsiya qilish haqida (lex.uz).

²⁵ More information about ratification/accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to international human rights instruments is available at: Treaty bodies Treaties (ohchr.org).

²⁶ More information about status of international human rights instruments by countries is available at: - OHCHR Dashboard.

²⁷ As of April 2022, 57 states are parties to the Convention. From CIS (The Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, only Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Azerbaijan, and Armenia are parties to it // more information is available at: - OHCHR Dashboard.

²⁸ As of April 2022, 68 states are parties to the Convention. From CIS (The Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, only Kazakhstan and Armenia are parties to it // more information is available at: - OHCHR Dashboard.

²⁹ Third periodic report submitted by Uzbekistan to the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights under articles 16 and 17 of the Covenant, due in 2019 (Date received: 19 June 2019) // available at: G1924220.pdf (un.org).

³⁰ E/C.12/UZB/CO/3: Concluding observations on the third periodic report of Uzbekistan // available at: OHCHR | E/C.12/UZB/CO/3: Concluding observations on the third periodic report of Uzbekistan.

tions. They are the Optional Protocol to the ICESCR³¹, the Optional Protocol to the CEDAW³², the Optional Protocol to the CAT³³, the Optional Protocol to CRC on a communications procedure³⁴, and the Optional Protocol to the CRPD³⁵.

The next field of human rights which Uzbekistan has not ratified any conventions is the status of refugees. In this sense, the Committee also recommends³⁶ the State party to establish national legal and policy frameworks in line with international standards for refugees and asylum seekers, to ensure their access to employment, social assistance, education, and health services. It also recommends that the State party accede to the Convention relating to the Status of Refugees³⁷, of 1951, and the Protocol relating to the Status of Refugees³⁸, of 1967, as well as to the Convention relating to the Status of Stateless Persons³⁹, of 1954, and the Convention on the Reduction of Statelessness, of 1961⁴⁰.

Encouragement for Uzbekistan to accede to the Refugee Convention was also mentioned by the State Department of the United States in its Uzbekistan 2020 Human Rights Report. It states that according to a 2018 UNHCR publication, Uzbekistan is the only country in Central Asia and the CIS that is not a signatory to the 1951 Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol. Furthermore, there is no national legislation to deal with asylum seekers and refugees. Rather, asy-

lum seekers are dealt with according to migration legislation⁴¹.

On the other hand, like other countries, there are several challenges and problems in implementation of the human rights instruments as well.

Regarding the implementation of the ICESCR, The Committee notes the adoption of the Act on the Legal Status of Foreign Citizens and Stateless Persons (No. ZRU-692 of 4 June 2021⁴²). The Committee is nevertheless concerned about the lack of a comprehensive legal and policy framework for refugees and asylum seekers, which hinders their access to economic and social rights (art. 2 (2))⁴³.

Concerning the implementation of the CERD, there is a still a challenge with the definition of racial discrimination and its incorporation into the national legislation of Uzbekistan. The Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination concluding observations on the combined tenth to twelfth reports of Uzbekistan, notes that the Committee is concerned that the State party has not yet incorporated in its legislation a definition of racial discrimination, with all the prohibited grounds, in line with article 1 of the Convention. While noting the position of the State party, the Committee reiterates its concerns about the lack of legislation of general application prohibiting racial discrimination and that such a prohibition is scattered in a variety of laws and confined to the

³¹ As of April 2022, 26 states are parties to the Optional Protocol. From CIS (The Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, only Armenia is a party to it, Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan are signatories // more information is available at:- OHCHR Dashboard.

³² As of April 2022, 114 states are parties to the Optional Protocol. From CIS (The Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, only Uzbekistan is not a party to it // more information is available at:- OHCHR Dashboard.

³³ As of April 2022, 92 states are parties to the Optional Protocol. From CIS (The Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, Armenia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Azerbaijan are parties to it // more information is available at:- OHCHR Dashboard.

³⁴ As of April 2022, 48 states are parties to the Optional Protocol. From CIS (The Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, only Armenia is a party to it // more information is available at:- OHCHR Dashboard.

³⁵ As of April 2022, 92 states are parties to the Optional Protocol. From CIS (The Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, only Turkmenistan and Azerbaijan are parties to it, and Armenia and Kazakhstan are signatories to it // more information is available at:- OHCHR Dashboard.

³⁶ E/C.12/UZB/CO/3: Concluding observations on the third periodic report of Uzbekistan, para. 23 // available at: OHCHR | E/C.12/UZB/CO/3: Concluding observations on the third periodic report of Uzbekistan.

³⁷ As of April 2022, 146 states are parties to the Convention. From the CIS (the Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, only the Republic of Uzbekistan does not participate in the Convention // More information is available at: UNTC.

³⁸ As of April 2022, 147 states are parties to the Convention. From the CIS (the Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, only the Republic of Uzbekistan does not participate in the Convention // More information is available at: UNTC.

³⁹ As of April 2022, 96 states are parties to the Convention. From the CIS (the Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, Armenia, Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan participate in the Convention // More information is available at: UNTC.

⁴⁰ As of April 2022, 78 states are parties to the Convention. From the CIS (the Commonwealth of Independent States) countries, Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Turkmenistan participate in the Convention // More information is available at: UNTC.

⁴¹ Uzbekistan 2020 Human Rights Report, State Department of the U.S., 2020 // available at: UZBEKISTAN-2020-HUMAN-RIGHTS-REPORT.pdf.

⁴² The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Legal Status of Foreign Citizens and Stateless Persons in the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-692 of 4 June 2021 // Available in Uzbek at: O'RQ-692-coh 04.06.2021. O'zbekiston Respublikasidachetelfuqarolariningvafuqaroligibo 'Imaganshaxslarninghuquqiyholatitog'risida (lex.uz).

⁴³ E/C.12/UZB/CO/3: Concluding observations on the third periodic report of Uzbekistan, para. 22 // available at: OHCHR | E/C.12/UZB/CO/3: Concluding observations on the third periodic report of Uzbekistan.

grounds of race and ethnicity. It is concerned that the status of anti-discrimination legislation still contains gaps and does not ensure adequate protection against and remedies for acts of racial discrimination in all areas of life (arts. 1 and 2)⁴⁴.

In this sense, the Committee recommends that the State party adopt a legislation of general application on the elimination of racial discrimination which incorporates a definition of racial discrimination in full conformity with article 1 of the Convention; prohibits direct and indirect discrimination in the enjoyment of all the rights set out in article 5 of the Convention, establishes remedies and redress mechanisms⁴⁵.

Regarding the implementation of the CAT, the main obstacle to the full implementation is that torture and ill-treatment continue to be committed by, at the instigation of and with the consent of the State party's law enforcement, investigative and prison officials, principally for the purpose of extracting confessions or information to be used in criminal proceedings.

In this sense, the Committee against Torture concludes observations on the fifth periodic report of Uzbekistan, and recommends that the State party should adopt further measures to ensure that prosecutors and judges ask all defendants in criminal cases whether they were tortured or ill-treated, that all allegations of torture and ill-treatment raised in judicial proceedings in the State party are promptly and effectively investigated and alleged perpetrators prosecuted and punished, and that no statement made as a result of torture or ill-treatment is invoked as evidence in any proceedings, except against the person accused of torture or ill-treatment as evidence that the statement was made under duress⁴⁶.

For example, human rights violations, particularly torture, have been reported in Uzbekistan during rapid search and investigation operations. This was announced by Deputy Prosecutor General Erkin Yuldashev at a meeting of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis on 21st of April 2022⁴⁷. According to Erkin Yuldashev, in

2021, the prosecutor's office received 308 complaints of torture. He stated that "in recent years, we have become increasingly involved in actions against torture, both domestically and internationally. We are putting into practice the positive experience of actions against torture in the world. Our laws are being amended in this regard. In 2021, we also worked hard on this issue. Last year, prosecutors received 308 complaints of torture and other ill-treatment. Of these, 13 were related to ill-treatment, 28 were related to physical and mental abuse, and 237 were related to injuries. All of these reports have been investigated and cracked down on. In particular, 21 criminal cases have been filed on torture and 28 employees have been prosecuted". Moreover, he added that in order to do that, the government needs to develop advanced evidence-gathering techniques and skills. First of all, it is necessary to improve the skills of investigators, as well as their mental health.

Moreover, concerning articles 4, and 12-16 of the CAT, the Committee recommends reviewing the laws and procedures governing compulsory medical treatment, including psychiatric confinement, and introduces safeguards to prevent its misuse by the authorities⁴⁸.

During the implementation of the CEDAW, the challenge can be seen in insufficient knowledge among the branches of government of the rights of women under the Convention, the concept of the substantive equality of women and men. Hence, the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women concluding observations on the fifth periodic report of Uzbekistan recommends that the State party ensures that the Convention is sufficiently known and applied by all branches of government, including the judiciary, as a framework for laws, court decisions and policies on gender equality and the advancement of women, and enhances women's awareness of their rights and the remedies available to them to claim violations of those rights under the Convention⁴⁹.

⁴⁴ CERD/C/UZB/CO/10-12: Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination: Concluding observations on the combined tenth to twelfth reports of Uzbekistan, para. 6 // Available at: OHCHR | CERD/C/UZB/CO/10-12: Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination: Concluding observations on the combined tenth to twelfth reports of Uzbekistan.

⁴⁵ Id. at para. 7.

⁴⁶ CAT/C/UZB/CO/5: Committee against Torture: Concluding observations on the fifth periodic report of Uzbekistan, para. 10 // Available at: OHCHR | CAT/C/UZB/CO/5: Committee against Torture: Concluding observations on the fifth periodic report of Uzbekistan.

⁴⁷ The Statement of the Deputy Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan Erkin Yuldashev at the meeting of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis, April 21, 2022 // Available in Uzbek at: "Tergovchilarimizongivatafakkurinisog'lomlashtirishkerak". Bosh prokuror o'rinbosaritergov jarayonidaqiynoqqo'llaganxodimlargajiddiychoralarko'rilganiniaytdi - Daryo.

⁴⁸ CAT/C/UZB/CO/5: Committee against Torture: Concluding observations on the fifth periodic report of Uzbekistan, para. 18(d) // Available at: OHCHR | CAT/C/UZB/CO/5: Committee against Torture: Concluding observations on the fifth periodic report of Uzbekistan.

⁴⁹ CEDAW/C/UZB/CO/5: Concluding observations on the fifth periodic report of Uzbekistan, para. 8 // Available at: OHCHR | CEDAW/C/UZB/CO/5: Concluding observations on the fifth periodic report of Uzbekistan.

Regarding the implementation of the recently ratified CRPD, the Republic of Uzbekistan enacted its national legislative act in 2020, which is based on international standards and the requirements of the UN Convention. However, among other provisions, it introduced the term “person with disability” instead of “disabled” and “invalid.”⁵⁰ To achieve a full implementation of the Convention, there are plenty of tasks to do for the government. For example, disability rights activists reported that discrimination occurred and estimated that approximately 8,500 adults with disabilities (of more than 631,000 between the ages of 16 and 60) were employed and approximately 75 percent lived below the poverty line in 2020.

The main source of problems and challenges in the implementation of international human rights conventions in the Republic of Uzbekistan could be the low level of legal knowledge among the population related to the content of these conventions and the practice of their application. The fact that some of the ratified conventions and optional protocols have not yet been translated into the Uzbek language makes it more difficult for the population to know and apply them where the most of the population’s native language is Uzbek (a state’s formal language too). For example, ICCPR-OP2-DP; CRC; CRC-OP-AC; CRC-OP-SC are not available in the Uzbek language in the official internet website of the Government (www.lex.uz) so that ordinary citizens can get to know and learn about them.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that since gaining independence, Uzbekistan adhering to the norms and principles of international law has made considerable progress in ratification and implementation of the core international human rights treaties. The fact that Uzbekistan has ratified 7 of the 9 most important international human rights conventions confirms the country’s firm position on the protection and promotion of human rights.

However, in order to further protect and promote human rights, as well as to apply international standards in specific areas of human rights to national leg-

islation, it would be appropriate to make the following recommendations.

Firstly, the respective governmental authorities and ministries are recommended to study the feasibility of the accession to the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families, and the International Convention for the Protection of All Persons from Enforced Disappearance.

Secondly, in order to simplify the procedural aspects and implementation of the Conventions as well as mitigating the process of inquiry and other crucial aspects for the residents to enjoy conventions, it is highly recommended to study the feasibility of the ratification/accession to the Optional Protocol to the ICESCR, the Optional Protocol to the CEDAW, the Optional Protocol to the CAT, the Optional Protocol to the CRC on a communications procedure, and the Optional Protocol to the CRPD.

Thirdly, in order to establish national legal and policy frameworks in line with international standards for refugees and asylum seekers, to ensure their access to employment, social assistance, education and health services, it is also recommended to study the feasibility of the accession to the Convention relating to the Status of Refugees, of 1951, and the Protocol relating to the Status of Refugees, of 1967, as well as possibility of the accession to the Convention relating to the Status of Stateless Persons, of 1954, and the Convention on the Reduction of Statelessness, of 1961.

Fourthly, it is recommended to accelerate the conformity of the national legislation with the provisions of the CAT, CERD, ICESCR and CRC.

Fifthly, in order to enhance knowledge and awareness of the population, it is highly recommended to provide them with the translation of the several human rights instrument in the Uzbek language (a state formal language) and accelerate the introduction training programs of human rights instruments to the different layers of the population.

Sixthly, it is important for the State to consider and implement the recommendations of the respective human rights committees on the promotion and better protection of human rights of people.

⁵⁰ The Law of The Republic of Uzbekistan on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, dated from October 15, 2020, No.LRU-641 // Available in English at: [LRU-641-сон 15.10.2020](http://www.lex.uz). On the rights of persons with disabilities ([lex.uz](http://www.lex.uz)).